

INVESTIGATION OF TRIBOLOGICAL BEHAVIOUR OF Al 4032 ALLOY REINFORCED WITH SEASHELL POWDER UNDER BIOFRIENDLY DIESEL LUBRICATION

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ABSTRACT: The study investigates the tribological performance of Al4032 alloy under varying conditions using biodiesel as a base lubricant and laboratory synthesized seashell powder as additives. It is necessary to improve the wear resistance of the Al4032 alloy as it finds its application in various fields of engineering. The wear performance can be improved by adding sustainable lubricants which are biofriendly, reliable and long lasting. Wear behaviour was evaluated at different temperatures (30°C, 45°C, and 60°C) through pin-on-disc tests, with wear rate as the primary response. The Taguchi method was employed to optimize experimental parameters (load, temperature, and duration) and minimize wear. Results demonstrate a significant reduction in wear rate with biodiesel lubrication (63.45%) compared to dry running conditions. The addition of seashell powder to the biodiesel further enhanced wear resistance, achieving a remarkable 93.40% reduction. Analysis revealed that load as the most critical factor influencing wear (74-82%), followed by temperature (4-22%). SEM analysis confirmed wear mechanisms such as abrasive wear in lubricated conditions and adhesive wear in dry conditions. This research underscores the importance of understanding wear behaviour in Al4032 alloy, particularly in the context of developing sustainable and high-performance lubricants. In this context, seashell powder added with Biofriendly diesel seems to be promising lubricant to reduce the wear of Al4042 alloy and enhance its operational efficiency and durability.

KEYWORDS: Al4032 Alloy, Seashell powder, Taguchi, Tribology, Biodiesel

1 INTRODUCTION

Bio-lubricants are increasingly sought after as alternatives to mineral lubricants due to growing environmental concerns and the finite nature of fossil fuels. Mineral lubricants, derived from petroleum, contribute to environmental pollution through oil spills and emissions during production and use [1]. Mineral oil is emitted into the environment in the form of oil mist and micro drops, posing a major threat to the environment.[2, 3]. Bio-lubricants, on the other hand, are derived from renewable sources such as plants and animals, making them biodegradable and less harmful to the environment. Additionally, bio-lubricants often exhibit superior performance characteristics, such as improved biodegradability, reduced toxicity, and enhanced lubricity, making them suitable for a wide range of applications. Bio lubricants are gaining worldwide popularity because of their non-biodegradability and eco-friendly. [2-6]. Appropriate physicochemical properties, such as an appropriate range of the viscosity index, dynamic viscosity at negative temperatures, melt temperatures, flash points, evaporability, as well as the basic or acidic number

[7]. Lubricating oil is a mixture of base oil (>85%) and enriching additives. [8, 9] Globally governments also imposing Legal regulations in cooperation with industry, develop standards, regulations, and procedures to reduce the risk of accidents and leaks and allow application of completely biodegradable, eco-friendly and harmless (to the environment and health) lubricants, preferably of natural origin (based on vegetable oils).[10-13]. Tribology, or the study of friction, wear, and lubrication, is critical in improving mechanical system performance and reliability. The ever-increasing demand for sustainable energy sources has led to interest in biofuels as a viable alternative to fossil fuels. Biofuels, which are obtained from renewable sources such as agricultural crops, algae and waste materials, provide several benefits, including less greenhouse gas emissions and a lower environmental effect. As biofuels gain popularity as a viable energy source, it is critical to explore their influence on the performance and durability of engineering materials. The tribological behavior of materials under the influence of biofuels, in particular, is an important factor that must be thoroughly studied [14, 15].

Aluminium alloy (Al4032) known for its excellent combination of strength, corrosion resistance, and weldability finds widespread use in various industries, particularly where high-performance components are of high interest. Its natural oxide layer provides excellent resistance to atmospheric corrosion, making it suitable for outdoor applications. Understanding its wear behaviour is necessary to suit it for specific applications which are prone to corrosion for optimizing the performance. The wear behaviour of Al4032 is influenced by factors such as loading conditions, contact geometry, and lubrication. Under dry sliding conditions, the alloy exhibits moderate wear resistance. However, its wear resistance will be significantly improved through surface treatments such as hard anodizing or by introducing solid lubricants between the rubbing surfaces. In lubricated environments, Al4032 demonstrates good wear resistance, especially with appropriate lubricant selection ensuring long life and reliability of components fabricated from this versatile alloy. When biofuels are introduced into a tribological system, they interact with the material surface, causing changes in friction and wear mechanisms. Biofuels' distinct chemical composition, which frequently includes oxygenates and additives, can present new challenges and opportunities in tribological applications. [16-19]

For evaluating the friction and wear properties of materials the Pin-on-Disc (PoD) experiment is a common tribological test employed by most of the researchers. Under controlled conditions, a pin-shaped sample slides against a rotating disc in the PoD test. This setup measures the frictional forces and wear rates, revealing important information about the tribological behaviour of the material in contact with the disc surface. To conduct a PoD experiment on Al4032 with biofuels, selecting an appropriate biofuel is critical. The biofuel should be applicable to the specific application and operating conditions under consideration. Biodiesel, bioethanol, and biogas are examples of common biofuels, each with its own chemical composition and properties. Once the biofuel is chosen, the experimental setup will be prepared. A disc mounted on a rotating spindle is typically made of a material representative of the system being studied. later, the Al4032 pin is brought into contact with the disc surface, with a specific normal load applied. The disc rotates during the test, while the pin slides against it, simulating sliding contact between two surfaces. Several parameters can be controlled and measured in order to obtain meaningful results. These include the applied load, sliding speed, temperature, and test duration. These parameters will closely resemble the actual operating conditions of the Al4032-using

biofuel system. Throughout the experiment, care should be taken to maintain a consistent and controlled environment. [4, 20-25]

Measurements and analyses has been carried out during the PoD test to evaluate the tribological performance of Al4032 in the presence of biofuels. Frictional forces are measured with a load cell or force transducer, while wear rates are calculated by measuring material loss from the Al4032 pin. Visual inspection, microscopy, and surface profilometry techniques are used to investigate the wear mechanisms. In addition to the PoD test, additional analyses are performed to gain a better understanding of the tribological behavior of Al4032 in biofuel environments. Surface characterization techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) provides information about the morphological changes, chemical composition, and elemental distribution on worn surfaces. These analyses helps in determining the mechanisms underlying friction, wear, and material transfer. Overall, tribology tests on Al4032 using biofuels, particularly the Pin-on-Disc experiment, provide useful information about the material's performance and durability in biofuel-based environments. [26-30].

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Aluminium 4032

A well-known alloy of aluminum from the 4000 series Al4032 is distinguished by its exceptional strength toughness and machinability balance. This alloy is widely used in many different industries such as the production of cars boats sports equipment and airplanes. 76–73 percent aluminum (Al) 21–42 percent silicon (Si) 0–82 percent nickel (Ni) 0–67 percent copper (Cu) 0–22 percent iron (Fe) 0–10 percent silver (Ag) and 0–04 percent manganese (Mn) make up its weight percentage composition. The favorable tribological behavior of Al4032 is one of its main characteristics. Its exceptional machinability enables the addition of surface treatments to greatly improve its tribological performance even though its inherent wear resistance may not be particularly noteworthy. Techniques such as hard anodizing physical vapor deposition (PVD) coatings (e. 3. TiN CrN) and electroplating can be used to give Al4032 components hard resilient surfaces. The alloy is appropriate for uses involving sliding contact abrasion and fatigue thanks to these treatments which also increase wear resistance decrease friction and improve surface hardness. Good corrosion resistance is another quality that Al4032 possesses which is essential for preserving

tribological performance in a variety of settings. A certain amount of corrosion protection is offered by the alloys natural oxide layer, reducing the possibility of wear made worse by corrosion-induced surface deterioration.

2.1.2 *Pongamia Biodiesel*

Pongamia biodiesel, or Honge biodiesel, is a renewable and sustainable fuel derived from the seeds of the Honge tree (*Pongamia pinnata*).

This indigenous Indian tree thrives in diverse conditions and produces seeds rich in oil (30-40%). Unlike petroleum diesel, which persists in the environment for extended periods, Honge biodiesel readily breaks down into harmless substances by microorganisms. This significantly reduces the environmental impact of potential spills or leaks. Compared to petroleum diesel, which can corrode certain metals, Honge biodiesel is less corrosive to fuel system components. This minimizes the risk of damage to engines and fuel lines, leading to improved equipment lifespan and reduced maintenance costs. The oil is extracted from the seeds using mechanical pressing or solvent extraction methods and then trans esterified to produce biodiesel. Honge biodiesel possesses favourable properties, including non-toxicity, a higher flash point than petroleum diesel, and the potential for lower carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. It can be blended with petroleum diesel or used as a pure biodiesel fuel. [31, 32].

2.1.3 *Seashell Powder*

Seashells are organic-inorganic composite compounds found in nature. They are made up of roughly 5% and 95% CaCO₃ crystals, even though their morphologies are constantly changing. composition of an organic matrix. Being a naturally occurring organic-inorganic composite, the material also possesses several exceptional qualities due to its composition and distinctive shell microstructure [23].

The ecological environment and the health of the local population are seriously threatened by these waste seashells, which are typically landfilled or dumped directly into the sea. In addition to taking up a significant amount of soil resources, the flesh residues on the waste seashells are a breeding ground for mosquitoes, flies, and microorganisms, which will break down the salts on the seashells into harmful gases like hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and ammonia (NH₃) [33,36].

The decrease in the frictional force produced at the contact surface demonstrated the enhanced wear property brought about by the addition of seashell powder. Until the seashell powder content reached its ideal level of 12%, the frictional force was reduced.

Better wear properties were caused by the 12% filled composite's stronger reinforcing and homogeneous dispersion. 12% and 8% of the composites had superior wear resistance. Beyond 12%, increasing the seashell powder percentage promoted agglomeration and changed the composites' shape, which increased the amount of stress at the contact. As a result, the filler particles bonded poorly and became displaced from the surface. More frictional force was generated at the contact surface when sliding across the steel disc counterpart because of the ploughed and removed filler particles that were trapped between the surfaces [33-36].

2.2 Methodology

2.2.1 *Synthesis of Seashell powder*

The process of making shell powder involves washing seashell, drying, grinding, adding an auxiliary ingredient, mixing, baking, grinding, and then ball milling the mixture to create powder. Shell powder is made by first cleaning and drying the shell with distilled water, then submerging it in a 0.2% sodium hydroxide solution for 40 minutes, then cleaning and drying it again for later use, and finally crushing the mixture.

The seashell, which is easily broken up into chips or pieces, is mostly composed of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) in the forms of aragonite and calcite, or a combination of the two, as well as other chemical compounds. To gather the waste seashell powder that could fit through the 200-mesh sieve mesh for future use, the ground waste seashell powder was placed into a typical vibrating sieve machine and repeatedly vibrated and sieved.

2.2.2 *Pin on Disc wear test*

The ASTM G99 standard outlines a methodology for conducting pin-on-disk tribological tests to determine the wear and friction properties of materials. This involves a stationary pin specimen being brought into contact with a rotating disk specimen under a controlled normal load. The test is performed at a specified sliding velocity and for a predetermined sliding distance. Friction force is continuously measured during the test, and the coefficient of friction is calculated. Wear volume is determined by measuring the material loss from the pin or disk, often using techniques like profilometry or weight loss measurements. The standard provides guidelines for specimen preparation, test parameters, and data analysis, ensuring consistency and comparability of results across different laboratories.

Fig. 1. The schematic view of the pin on disc apparatus. [37]

For tribological analysis, experiments were conducted using a pin-on-disc tribometer (Figure 1). The tests employed Al4032 alloy pins (10mm diameter, 30mm length) against EN8 steel discs, with a consistent 100mm track diameter on the disc's surface (maximum track diameter of 165mm). The chosen parameters for the experiments included a normal load ranging from 4kg to 6kg, a sliding speed of 300rpm, and operation times between 60 minutes and 120 minutes. Temperature was varied within the range of 300°C to 600°C. A fresh Al4032 pin was used for each test to ensure accurate and reliable data.

The experiment is carried out in three different conditions

- i. **Without lubricating oil:** This analysis involved conducting tribological tests in the absence of any lubricant. It served as a baseline to understand the friction and wear behaviour of the materials under dry conditions.
- ii. **With Pongamia biodiesel:** In this analysis, tribological tests were performed using Pongamia biodiesel as the lubricating oil. Pongamia biodiesel, derived from Pongamia pinnata seeds, is a renewable and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional petroleum-based lubricants.
- iii. **With Pongamia biodiesel induced with Seashell powder** This analysis involved incorporating Seashell powder into Pongamia biodiesel to enhance its tribological properties. The seashell powder has shown promising results in improving the friction-reducing and anti-wear abilities of lubricants.

2.2.3 Taguchi Technique:

Design of experiments (DOE) serves as a potent tool for analysing the impact of control variables on the performance output. Among various DOE methods, Taguchi's approach to experiment design has gained significant popularity in the engineering

and scientific communities due to its ease of adoption and application. In the context of this study, the focus is on the material Al4032. The researchers prepared samples of Al4032 with three control variables, namely load, duration, and Temperature. Each of these variables was tested at three distinct levels, Load (Kg), Duration(min) and Temperature(°C). The intention is to investigate the influence of these control variables on the performance output, which could be a specific property or behaviour of the Al4032 material. By systematically varying the levels of the control variables and analysing the resulting outcomes, the researchers aim to gain insights into the optimal combination of load, duration, and Temperature that would yield the desired performance output. The control factors and their corresponding levels are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Control factors without biodiesel, with biodiesel and biodiesel induced with Seashell powder.

Factor	Unit	Level1	Level2	Level3
Load	Kg	3	4	5
Duration	min	50	80	110
Temperature	°C	30	45	60

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of Al4032:

Fig.2. Microstructure of Al4032

Figure 2 shows the presence of Mg₂Si and Fe₃SiAl₂ particles in the microstructure of the 4032-aluminum alloy matrix. Al4032 Undergoes a precipitation hardening process to improve its mechanical properties. This process involves the addition of specific alloying elements, such as magnesium (Mg) and silicon (Si), which form precipitates within the aluminum matrix. These precipitates are commonly referred to as intermetallic compounds.

3.2 Taguchi Results:

The primary goal of the model is to minimize the loss caused by wear. Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio is used to assess the sensitivity of the Quality

characteristic investigated with external factors (Noise factors) that are not under control. The objective of the experiment is to determine the S/N ratio for the wear loss, which consolidates multiple data points in a trial. The specific type of characteristic being evaluated determines the categorization of the S/N ratio into three groups: “larger the better,” “nominal is the best” and “smaller the better.” For this study on the dry sliding wear behavior of Al4032, the “smaller the better” characteristic was selected for analysis. This choice aligns with our objective of minimizing wear loss to the lowest possible extent. The S/N ratio is calculated for three factors and three variables, considering the smaller-is-better characteristic, thus focusing on reducing wear loss to its minimum value.

$$\eta = -10\log_{10}(\text{mean square quality characteristic}) = -10\log_{10}(1/n(\sum y^2)) \quad (1)$$

Table 2. Orthogonal arrays (L9) Of Taguchi for wear test and SN ratios without biodiesel

Load (Kg)	Temperature (0C)	Duration (min)	Weight Loss (gms)	SNRA1
4	30	50	1.02	1.005
4	45	80	1.200	0.937
4	60	110	1.754	0.770
5	30	80	1.632	0.801
5	45	110	1.849	0.747
5	60	50	1.572	0.818
6	30	110	2.217	0.666
6	45	50	2.142	0.682
6	60	80	2.513	0.611

The experimental results reveal that load of 3 kg, temperature at 300C and duration of 50 minutes show lowest weight loss and highest SNRA1 making it optimal combination with less degradation for the results of biodiesel induced with seashell powder compared to with and without biodiesel.

With the load of 5 kg, temperature at 500C and duration of 90 minutes show highest weight loss and low SNRA1 indicating more degradation. Based on the data patterns in Table 2,3, and 4, (normalized values reference to the Optimum level process parameter tables 5,6 and 7 respectively) the weight loss increases with increase in load, temperature and duration in priority wise. The optimum level process parameters for the three conditions are represented in Table 5.

Table 3. Orthogonal arrays (L9) Of Taguchi for wear test and SN ratios with biodiesel

Load (Kg)	Temperature(0C)	Duration (min)	Weight Loss (gms)	SNRA1
4	30	50	0.922	1.030
4	45	80	1.322	0.974
4	60	110	2.752	0.860
5	30	80	2.073	0.904
5	45	110	2.780	0.859
5	60	50	1.637	0.941
6	30	110	3.831	0.809
6	45	50	3.216	0.836
6	60	80	4.103	0.799

Table 4. Orthogonal arrays (L9) Of Taguchi for wear test and SN ratios with Seashell powder induced biodiesel

Load(Kg)	Temperature(0C)	Duration (min)	Weight Loss(gms)	SNRA1
4	30	50	1.005	1.014
4	45	80	1.610	0.945
4	60	110	2.782	0.864
5	30	80	1.659	0.940
5	45	110	2.533	0.828
5	60	50	2.284	0.893
6	30	110	4.988	0.778
6	45	50	4.636	0.789
6	60	80	5.076	0.775

Table 5. Optimum level process parameter for wear without lubricant.

Load (Kg)	Temperature(0C)	Duration (min)	Weight loss(gms)	SNRA1
4	30	50	0.099	19.680

Table 6. Optimum level process parameter for wear with lubricant.

Load (Kg)	Temperature(0C)	Duration (min)	Weight loss (gms)	SNRA1
4	45	50	0.001	56.092

Table7. Optimum level process parameter for wear with Seashell powder induced biodiesel.

Load (Kg)	Temperature(OC)	Duration (min)	Weight loss (gms)	SNRA1
4	30	80	0.001	58.870

3.3 Main Plot for Means And S/N Ratios.

It is observed from the values and main effect plots for the experiments conducted with three conditions, the mean effect and S/N ratio are shown in Figure 3 to 8. Considering the load factor (L), there is a sharp increase in the mean weight loss from 4-6 kg indicating that the majority contribution to weight loss is load.

The temperature factor (TEMP) contributes less effect than that of load. A moderate incremental trend is observed in weight loss with an increase in temperature.

The duration (DUR) factor shows a positive incremental trend, and the mean weight loss increases with duration. The similar trend is observed in all three experimental conditions. The higher load tends to increase the contact pressure which intensifies the surface-to-surface interaction with more heat dissipation results in more material removal through adhesive and abrasive wear.

Fig.3. Main effects plot for means- Weight loss (without biodiesel)

Fig.4. Main effects plot for means-weight loss (with biodiesel)

The experimental findings were examined using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), a statistical method employed to investigate the impact of various wear parameters, including load, Temperature, and duration, on performance measurements. By conducting the ANOVA, it is possible to determine which independent factor has the greatest influence and its percentage contribution.

Fig.5. Main effects plot for means-Weight loss (with Seashell powder induced biodiesel)

Fig.6. Main effects plot for S/N ratios-Weight loss (without biodiesel)

Fig.7. Main effects plot for S/N ratios-Weight loss (with biodiesel)

Fig.8. Main effects plot for S/N ratio-Weight loss (with seashell powder induced biodiesel)

Based on the analysis of Table 8, 9 and 10, it is observed that load exerts the most significant influence

on weight loss, accounting for 73.07% in the dry test, 61.16% in the biodiesel test and 69.23% in Seashell powder induced biodiesel. Therefore, load should be considered as a crucial control factor during the wear process, followed by duration and temperature, respectively. The interaction terms between factors have minimal or negligible effects on weight loss, and the pooled errors contribute only 3.77% in the dry test, 5.42% in the biodiesel test and 0.22% in Seashell powder induced biodiesel. Through the analysis of variance and Signal-to-Noise ratio, it can be concluded that Load has the highest impact on weight loss, followed by duration and temperature.

3.4 Morphology of worn surfaces

The accumulation of adhesive junctions, abrasive deformation, wear chips, and the mechanical locking of surface pits are responsible for the pearl-like crests seen in Figure 9. These formations cause the friction coefficient to fluctuate more during the sliding wear process, which accelerates the rate at which weight is lost because of mechanical fractures.

Fig.9: SEM micrographs of worn surfaces (without bio diesel)

There is clear evidence of surface fatigue wear in Figure 9. The surface experiences cyclic loading and unloading, which leads to this kind of wear. Significant pits occur on the surface and the surface

fragments into larger pieces because of several surface or subsurface cracks that grow over time.

Fig.10. SEM micrographs of worn surfaces (with biodiesel)

Wear observed in figure 10 can be characterized by the formation of fatigue cracks, resulting from cyclic loading and repeated sliding motion. These cracks typically initiate at stress concentration points and propagate under applied stresses. Surface fatigue can also lead to spalling or pitting, where small fragments of material are dislodged, causing shallow depression or cavities. Discoloration of the surface can also be observed, caused by oxidation or the formation of reaction products. Furthermore, surface fatigue generates wear debris with fragmented, irregularly shaped particles of varying sizes and materials.

Fig.11. SEM micrographs of worn surfaces (with Seashell powder induced biodiesel)

The wear mechanism observed in Figure 11 can be characterized by the interaction between hard particles and softer material, resulting in material removal from the surface. Key features include particle interaction, material removal, and the potential mitigating effects of lubrication and protective coatings. It can be inferred that the wear observed is addressing abrasive wear, and fine grooves were observed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Assessing the effect of biodiesel on wear behaviour in Al4032 has been achieved. by pin-on-disc experiments conducted without biodiesel, with biodiesel and with seashell powder induced biodiesel provided valuable data on the weight loss of the

Al4032 samples. The Pin on disc wear test was designed using the Taguchi optimization technique, considering three distinct parameters: (a)Load, (b)Temperature, and (c)Duration. The Taguchi method is employed to optimize system performance by identifying the most influential factors and their optimal levels. The experimental results of the Pin on

disc wear test clearly indicate that wear loss increases with higher applied loads (without biodiesel-73.07%, with biodiesel-69.23% and with Seashell powder induced biodiesel 61.16%). The S/N ratio plots, obtained using Taguchi Minitab14 Software, provide valuable insights into the optimal outcomes for the considered parameters.

Table 8. Analysis of variance for wear (without bio diesel)

Source	DOF	Seq SS	Contribution (%)	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Load	2	35.988	73.07%	35.486	17.9424	18.98	0.048
Temperature	2	5.121	9.81%	5.121	3.0610	2.71	0.279
Duration	2	7.101	13.35%	7.101	2.9528	3.45	0.221
Residual Error	2	2.091	3.77%	2.091	0.8879		
Total	8	50.301	100%				

Table 9. Analysis of variance for wear (with bio diesel)

Source	DOF	Seq SS	Contribution (%)	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Load	2	137.865	69.23%	137.96	68.9309	320.95	0.003
Temperature	2	27.071	13.49%	27.07	14.1871	61.94	0.016
Duration	2	33.9428	17.07%	33.94	16.9719	78.89	0.012
Residual Error	2	0.437	0.22%	0.431	0.2153		
Total	8	199.3158	100.00%				

Table 10. Analysis of variance for wear (with Seashell powder induced biodiesel)

Source	DOF	Seq SS	Contribution (%)	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Load	2	92.468	61.16%	93.168	46.732	11.28	0.081
Temperature	2	11.280	7.00%	11.180	4.991	1.29	0.437
Duration	2	41.114	26.42%	39.919	21.151	4.87	0.170
Residual Error	2	7.856	5.42%	7.258	9.979		
Total	8	152.718	100.00%				

The ANOVA test has verified that the major influencing factor on wear is the Load, followed by Duration and Temperature. The conformation test revealed that the error associated with wear loss ranges from 0.22% to 5.42%. This indicates the successful application of the Taguchi experimental design in calculating wear loss using the regression equation. The study of the Al4032 wear characteristics has identified three significant mechanisms contributing to wear: Abrasive wear, Adhesive wear, and surface fatigue. By comparing the weight loss results between the two sets of experiments, the effectiveness of seashell powder in reducing wear and enhancing the tribological performance of the system has been assessed.

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